

ACGS variant classification guidelines supplementary information

Supplementary Table S1: Additional information for pathogenic (P) and benign (B) codes usage in SNV guidelines to supplement ACMG/AMP guidelines

Evidence criteria (level) supplementary notes
<p>PVS1 – Null variant (nonsense, frameshift, canonical ± 1 or 2 splice sites, initiation codon, single or multi-exon deletion or duplication) in a gene where LOF is a known mechanism of disease; and non-canonical splice variants where RNA analysis confirms aberrant transcription.</p> <p>The evidence strength level can be modified depending upon the variant type, location within the gene or any additional evidence for the likelihood of a true null effect. A PVS1 decision tree has been developed by the ClinGen Sequence Variant Interpretation group to support the interpretation of loss of function variants (1) and modified for splicing variants by the Splicing SVI (2). In addition, multiple VCEPs have developed gene-specific PVS1 decision trees. In addition, see Figure 1 for ACGS-adapted PVS1 decision tree included non-stop decay, gain-of-function truncating variants in last exon, revised weighting for whole exon duplications and other modifications.</p> <p>The PVS1 decision tree (1) “assumes that the gene/disease association is at a Moderate, Strong, or Definitive clinical validity level (3)” in addition to LOF being a known mechanism of disease. Gene-disease validity curations at these levels are currently available for >3600 genes (https://search.clinicalgenome.org/kb/gene-validity). When reviewing curations, it is important to note the date of last evaluation, as curations reflect a temporally static assessment. New evidence may have emerged since the date of last evaluation, either supporting or refuting the original assessment. It is not essential to perform a formal curation for every gene not yet on this list, but laboratories are expected to establish that there is sufficient evidence for the gene/disease association in addition to the LOF mechanism before applying the PVS1 criterion.</p> <p>Before applying PVS1 it is important to consider rescue mechanisms for premature termination codons (PTC) e.g. alternate splicing and whether the exon is present in all clinically relevant transcripts.</p> <p><u>Small sequence variants:</u></p> <p>Note that caution is required when interpreting 3' nonsense or frameshift variants in the last exon or the last 50bp of the penultimate exon, as these are predicted to escape nonsense mediated decay (NMD). For example the <i>BRCA2</i> nonsense variant c.9976A>T p.(Lys3326Ter) results in loss of the last 93 amino acids of the BRCA2 protein but does not confer a high or moderate risk of familial breast cancer (4).</p> <p>Variants resulting in a premature termination codon within the first 200bp of the coding sequence may not be targeted for NMD, and re-initiation of translation may occur using an alternate start codon. The exact NMD boundary is gene-specific and may lie between 100-200bp (5, 6). If there is a potential in-frame initiation codon downstream, the missing N-terminal region of the protein should be assessed according to the principles described in the decision tree (1) (i.e. is the missing region critical to protein function / is it >10% of the entire protein length / are there any reported pathogenic variants upstream of the potential initiation codon) and apply PVS1 at either reduced strength or n/a, as appropriate. If no alternative in-frame start codon is identified 5' of key domains, use PVS1 at maximum strength.</p> <p>DECIPHER (https://www.deciphergenomics.org/) protein/genomic display tab shows predicted regions of NMD escape for specific transcripts. PVS1 can also be used for stop loss variants that abolish the canonical termination codon. In the absence of an in-frame termination codon in the 3'UTR the mRNA transcript is likely to undergo nonstop mediated decay (NSD) and PVS1 up to very strong can be used. If there is an in-frame termination codon within the 3'UTR then the predicted consequence is a protein with additional amino acids and PM4 (protein length change) can be used (see Figure S1).</p> <p>Frameshift variants in the last exon that cause an alteration to, and extension of coding sequence, and are not predicted to undergo NMD or NSD should follow guidance in (1) (PVS1_strong, PVS1_moderate or N/A depending on functional significance of region and proportion of protein affected).</p> <p><u>Copy number and structural variants:</u></p> <p>PVS1 may be applied to copy number variants that partially overlap a single causative gene:</p> <p>For deletions that include the 5' untranslated region (UTR) the evidence strength level should reflect whether the deleted interval includes coding sequence or is restricted solely to the 5'UTR. Deletions that include the whole of</p>

the 5'UTR and first coding exon, or additional coding exons, are typically deleterious in LOF genes and PVS1 at maximum strength can usually be applied. If an alternative isoform is not encompassed by the deletion, downgrade the strength of PVS1 accordingly.

If the deletion interval involves only the 5'UTR, with no additional evidence for this region, PVS1 should not be applied. Where the deletion of a 5'UTR encompasses a well-established core promoter and transcription start site and there is evidence supporting the role of 5'UTR variants in disease, it is likely to be deleterious. However, as some genes have multiple isoforms with multiple promoters, enhancers and transcription start sites we recommend use of PVS1 at maximum strength of strong, depending on robustness of the supporting evidence. Where functional evidence is available confirming a null, loss-of-function effect for a 5'UTR deletion, PVS1 can be upgraded to very strong.

Deletions that partially overlap the 3'UTR and extend to include the entire untranslated region, the last exon, and additional upstream exons are expected to trigger nonsense-mediated decay (NMD); therefore, PVS1 at very strong is appropriate. If the partially overlapping 3' deletion involves only the last exon, the evidence strength level depends on whether this exon is known to be critical for protein function. PVS1 up to maximum strength may be applied if there is evidence that loss of this region is disease-causing/affects a critical domain. If such evidence is lacking, PVS1_mod should be applied. Where the deletion encompasses only the 3'UTR, PVS1 should not be applied, unless there is published or functional evidence that loss of the 3' UTR is pathogenic.

The pathogenicity of partial overlapping duplications at the 5' or 3' end of a gene is influenced by their orientation, genomic location, and structural impact. Tandem duplications including a UTR in direct orientation that preserve the reading frame are typically considered non-deleterious and are usually classified as non-reportable variants of uncertain significance (VUS). Exceptions may arise when evidence supports an alternative pathogenic mechanism. For example, if the phenotype is highly specific to the gene in question, further investigation into disruption of key uORF or promoter sequence, expression analysis or aberrant splicing may be warranted. For example, a recurrent pathogenic *MSH2* exon 1-6 duplication including promoter region with supporting RNA evidence demonstrating use of duplicated upstream promoter and splicing of exon 6 of duplicated region to exon 2 of gene causing PTC (ACGS laboratory data). As per the PVS1 decision tree, proven tandem duplications that disrupt reading frame can be coded up to PVS1 very strong. Where the location or orientation of the duplication is unknown (e.g. breakpoints unclear or detected by a method which is only sensitive to dosage such as microarray or MLPA) or where its impact on reading frame is unclear (e.g. inverted duplications, duplications inserted into other genes), scientific judgement is required to assess the strength of the evidence, including specificity of phenotype and predicted (but unproven) reading frame impacts. PVS1 should generally not be applied above strong in such circumstances. PVS1 should not be used for duplications identified in genes with non-specific phenotypes where the impact on reading frame is completely unclear. Where further clarification of phenotypic features or breakpoint resolution has the potential to raise a suspicious VUS duplication to likely pathogenic status, all effort should be made to undertake the additional work required.

Increasingly, the use of whole genome and long-read sequencing enables the detection and characterisation of complex and structural variants not explicitly covered in the ClinGen SVI guidance(1) such as inversions, translocations, insertions, and mobile repeat element insertions. Where such changes impact single genes, we recommend applying PVS1 at appropriate strength based upon the predicted impact on the protein reading frame.

Splicing variants:

New guidelines from the ClinGen SVI splicing subgroup (2) recommend use of PVS1_strength (RNA) for splice variants where RNA studies have confirmed an aberrant splicing profile that can be interpreted using the PVS1 decision tree. PVS1(RNA) is to be used in place of PS3 for splicing assays including RNA analysis from patient material or use of a minigene splicing assay. Considerations for splicing assay design and interpretation of splicing results are included in table S9 of (2). These include RNA source, use of normal controls, technology etc. Scientific judgement should be used in experimental design and should consider practicalities and the specific clinical question being addressed. The SVI also have a feedback document that should be used as an official addendum to their guidelines: https://clinicalgenome.org/site/assets/files/9588/clingen_svi_splicing_subgroup_dynamic_document_-_response_to_feedback.pdf.

The SVI recommends upgrading PVS1 to very strong for in-frame RNA skipping events encompassing undisputed clinically relevant residues. PVS1 should not be used for variants for which there is a plausible rescue model, based on observation of naturally occurring alternative spliced transcripts e.g. *BRCA1* c.594-2A>C splice acceptor site variant is benign due to the in-frame transcript being a naturally occurring functional isoform (7).

PVS1 should not be used for non-canonical splice site variants in the absence of RNA studies.

The effect of canonical splice variants at the first and final intron donor/acceptor sites can be difficult to predict. The surrounding sequence should be checked for cryptic splice sites and downgrade evidence if uncertain. See figure 2 of (2).

Care should be taken with splice sites predicted to lead to an in-frame transcript or use an alternative cryptic in-frame splice site. Such variants require additional evidence that the region is critical to protein function. Using

SpliceAI with an expanded window of 5000bp (8) or SpliceAI-10K (9) is recommended to predict all splicing events including pseudoexonisation.

+2T>C splice variants may result in functional GC-AG splice sites and PVS1 should be used cautiously in the absence of RNA studies, particularly in the context of cancer predisposition genes where reduced penetrance and lack of phenotype specificity can complicate variant interpretation (10) e.g. *BRCA2* c.8331+2T>C (11) and *BAP1* c.783+2T>C.(12) Use of SpliceAI is recommended to assess the likely impact on splicing; PVS1 should be cautiously applied for +2T>C variants with SpliceAI delta score <0.8 in the absence of RNA evidence.

Approximately 1.5% of natural splice sites use a C at +2 (GC splice site) therefore a +2C>T variant is likely to increase the efficiency of the splice site and PVS1 is n/a - use of SpliceAI is recommended to confirm prediction.

For variants not undergoing NMD or showing incomplete (leaky) splicing, functional evidence under PS3 may also be used to support pathogenicity, but the combined evidence from PVS1 plus PS3 should be capped at 8 points. Where gain-of-function (GOF) is the predicted mechanism of disease, PVS1 should not be used. For truncating variants in the last exon of a gene causing GOF effect see PM4.

PVS1 should not be used with PM1, PM4, PP2, PP3.

PS1 – Same amino acid change as a previously established pathogenic variant regardless of nucleotide change and splicing variants within the same motif with identical predicted effect

This criterion can be used if there is sufficient evidence for pathogenicity for the same missense variant (i.e. an amino acid change) caused by a **different** base substitution. For example the previously reported variant is p.(Val12Leu) (c.34G>**C**) and your patient's variant is p.(Val12Leu) (c.34G>**T**) as described by (13). PS1_moderate can be applied if the other variant reaches a classification of likely pathogenic. Care should be applied to avoid inappropriate use of this criterion when aberrant splicing is the most likely mechanism of pathogenicity for a putative missense variant.

PS1 may also be used for initiation codon variants where a different nucleotide substitution affecting the initiation codon has been classified as pathogenic and at moderate level where the variant is classified as likely pathogenic.

The ClinGen SVI splicing subgroup (2) also allows use of PS1 (sup, mod or str) for variants within the same splicing motif or region (donor motif = last 3 bases of the exon and 3–6 nucleotides of intronic sequence adjacent to the exon and acceptor motif = first base of the exon and 3–20 nucleotides upstream from the exon boundary) with same predicted impact. Strength levels also depend on whether the comparison variant is pathogenic or likely pathogenic and the PVS1 weight applicable to the variant under assessment.

PS1 should not be used with PM4.

PS2/PM6 – De novo (both maternity and paternity confirmed) in a patient with the disease and no family history

This evidence may be provided either from the patient undergoing testing or a previously identified case. Note that the genotype **must be consistent** with the phenotype. Mosaicism in either a patient or their parent is evidence of a *de novo* event. If a *de novo* variant was identified by trio exome or genome sequencing, then maternity and paternity will already have been confirmed by using a bioinformatics pipeline that would reveal inconsistencies with inheritance. In the situation that a *de novo* variant is identified by trio exome or genome sequencing a cautious approach is recommended since every exome/genome typically contains multiple *de novo* non-synonymous variants. If the patient's phenotype is non-specific or there is evidence of significant genetic heterogeneity (e.g. intellectual disability), this criterion should only be used at a lower level. See **Supplementary Table S3** for examples.

A points-based system has been developed by the ClinGen Sequence Variant Interpretation group to enable this criterion to be used at a stronger level for variants that have been shown to have arisen *de novo* in multiple index cases and with differing phenotypic specificity:

https://clinicalgenome.org/site/assets/files/3461/svi_proposal_for_de_novo_criteria_v1_1.pdf.

If PS2/PM6 is applied, the specificity of that patient's phenotype to the relevant disorder, should be captured using an increased strength of PS2/PM6, rather than applying a separate and additional line of evidence within PP4.

PS3 – Well-established *in vitro* or *in vivo* functional studies supportive of a damaging effect on the gene or gene product

For use with variant specific protein functional assays only. For gene specific assays e.g. enzyme assay on tissue sample, use phenotypic specificity criterion PP4. Protein modelling studies are not considered sufficient evidence for this criterion but may be incorporated in PM1.

Use of RNA splicing assays has now moved to PVS1(RNA). PS3 should only be applied for well-established assays assessing the impact on protein function not captured by RNA-splicing assays (e.g. *in vitro* or cellular assays) (2).

Functional studies can include *in vitro* functional assays for specific variants, for example reporter gene assays for transcription factors or Multiplexed Assays of Variant Effect (MAVEs) including saturation genome editing to

assay multiple variants at scale. ClinGen SVI have produced effective guidelines on application of *in vitro* protein based assays for PS3/BS3 using statistical analysis based on the number of true positive and true negative controls used in the assays and assessment of the quality and confidence of variant-specific assays (14). They include a calculator in the supplementary information which can be used to calculate the odds of pathogenicity and equivalent strength of PS3/BS3.

Multiple functional datasets from Multiplexed Assays of Variant Effect (MAVEs) including those generated by deep mutational scanning (DMS) or massively parallel reporter assay (MPRA) experiments are now available on <https://www.mavedb.org/>. The MaveMD interface integrates these functional data with ClinVar submissions, clinical evidence calibrations, visualisations, and structured evidence compatible with ACMG/AMP variant classification guidelines. However, careful review is required to ensure all disease mechanisms (e.g. splicing) and protein functions are included and to assess the provenance and quality of the truthsets used to calibrate these assays. These datasets can be particularly valuable when interpreting variants identified in individuals with non-European genetic ancestry, who are underrepresented in large databases such as gnomAD and Clinvar. Continued development of educational resources will be essential to support clinical application of these powerful and rapidly evolving datasets in variant classification.

Scientific judgement is still required to assess evidence from other approaches which do not fit this framework (e.g. animal models).

PS3 and PP3 can be applied together for missense variants as the functional assay is assessing protein function/activity and *in silico* tools assess evolutionary conservation, therefore are considered independent.

PS4 – The prevalence of the variant in affected individuals is significantly increased compared with the prevalence in controls

Where large cohort studies and meta-analyses are available, a useful resource for calculating odds ratios and confidence intervals to support the use of PS4_Strong is located at https://www.medcalc.org/calc/odds_ratio.php. gnomAD population data can be used for the control population, although caution may be appropriate when there are many cases of the disorder included in the data set, for example in cardiovascular diseases. Care should also be taken to ensure that case and control populations are ethnically matched where this is possible; note that certain sub-populations are poorly represented in gnomAD.

Case control study data is rarely available for rare diseases, but PS4 can be used as a **moderate** level of evidence if the variant has been *previously identified in multiple (two or more) unrelated affected individuals* or as a **supporting** level of evidence if *previously identified in one unrelated affected individual*, with a **rare and specific phenotype**, and variant is very rare in gnomAD v4.1 (see Note 2 in Table 3(13)). In practice this is most applicable to severe, paediatric onset, autosomal dominant disorders where absence or extreme rarity in the gnomAD database allows use of both PM2 and PS4. For more common or later onset autosomal dominant disorders, variants with a low frequency in gnomAD, consistent with disease prevalence and severity/age-of onset, should ideally undergo case-control analysis to determine an odds ratio. Where no case-control analysis is possible, and there are a significant number of reports in the literature of affected patients, showing increased prevalence in patients, PS4 can still be cautiously applied in the absence of PM2.

For recessive disorders it is recommended to use PM3 to count rare biallelic cases (if information on their genotype is available), rather than PS4. However, for more common recessive variants, case-control analysis using PS4 may be required to demonstrate enrichment in affected patients versus controls.

For semi-dominant genes e.g. *LDLR*, *F11*, *VWF* data from both monoallelic and biallelic cases can be combined and used under both PS4 and PM3 respectively.

PM1 – Located in a mutational hot spot and/or critical and well-established functional domain (e.g. active site of an enzyme) without benign variation

Useful plots of functional domains, gnomAD variants and reported disease-causing variants for a region of a gene are available on the DECIPHER website. *In silico* protein modelling data can be included as evidence.

Evidence of lack of assumed benign missense variation (e.g. depletion of missense variants in the local region in gnomAD) may support PM1 but is insufficient evidence alone for its application (this should generally be applied in the PP2 criterion); at a minimum, one or more of the following should be apparent for PM1 to be applicable:

- Evidence of significant local enrichment of pathogenic missense variation
- Evidence from protein or protein domain paralogs of pathogenic variation at the paralogous residue
- Evidence that the residue lies in an invariant position in a functionally well-established domain (e.g. enzyme active site)
- Evidence from *in silico* protein modelling studies predicting a likely deleterious structural or ligand-binding impact in a region of the protein with a known function

For regions showing a clear enrichment of pathogenic missense variation but some local benign variation and/or where the functional significance of the protein domain is not well-established, PM1 should typically not be applied above supporting level.

PM1 may also be applied at supporting level for well-established functional non-coding loci with compelling evidence of a likely impact on gene expression at transcriptional or translational level(15). This can include variants that impact known functionally or structurally relevant nucleotides in non-coding RNA genes (e.g. *RNU4ATAC*, *SNORD118*). However, the use of PM1 is not appropriate for variants predicted to result in premature termination codons or splicing effects.

PM1 may be upgraded to strong for very specific residues that are critical for protein structure or function. Examples include *FBN1* - affects invariant cysteine in EGF-like calcium-binding domain, *NOTCH3* - Cysteine substitutions that result in an uneven number of cysteine residues within an EGF-like repeat, Cysteine or Histidine substitutions in C2H4 zinc fingers such as *GLI3*. Glycine substitutions in the triple helix of collagen genes such as *COL1A1* may also warrant application of PM1_str. However, caution should be applied when upgrading PM1 for novel Gly-X-Y substitutions in collagen genes especially where the triple helical domain is very large/there insufficient evidence. The evidence should be evaluated on a case-by-case basis as not all collagen Glycine changes are disease causing (ACGS internal data).

Do not use the same evidence to code PM1 and PM5 or PP2, but the two codes can be used together if each supported by independent evidence.

PM2 – Absent from controls (or at extremely low frequency if recessive) in Genome Aggregation Database

In a 2020 recommendation, ClinGen Sequence Variant Interpretation (SVI) Working Group proposed reducing the weight of PM2 to “supporting” by default ([SVI Recommendation for Absence/Rarity \(PM2\) - Version 1.0](#)). The recommendation also indicated that future adjustments to other criteria would be necessary to accommodate the change in PM2 weight. In previous ACGS guidelines, there was continued support for application of PM2 at moderate level, pending a fuller revision of the ACMG guidance. An ACGS mini-impact assessment (Supplementary data S5) has been undertaken to assess the effect of downgrading PM2, along with the proposed changes to PP3/BP4 (16). Based on these results (see supplementary data S5: PM2 mini-impact assessment) **we recommend no change to PM2 mod use should be implemented, pending the new ACMG v4.0 guidelines.**

Scientific judgement may be applied in the situation that the variant is sufficiently rare within gnomAD (rather than absent) for an autosomal dominant disorder where a very low frequency of heterozygotes is consistent with the disease prevalence, penetrance, genetic and allelic heterogeneity. A very useful tool is available at <http://cardiodb.org/allelefrequencyapp/> (17) to calculate gene-specific allele frequencies and counts for BA1/BS1. The allele frequency/allele count for PM2 is recommended to be at least a factor of 10 below BS1.

PM2 can be used for autosomal or X-linked recessive disorders if there are rare homozygotes/hemizygotes in the relevant gnomAD datasets and the allele frequency is a factor of 10 below BS1, is not greater than would be predicted for a benign variant and consistent with the disease prevalence, penetrance, genetic and allelic heterogeneity.

Application of PM2 at supporting level may be appropriate where a variant is extremely rare in gnomAD but the published population genetics of the disorder are not sufficiently robust to perform reliable calculations of allele frequency.

Somatic mosaicism of variants in some genes (e.g. *TP53*, *DNMT3A* and *ASXL1*) during hematopoietic clonal expansion (CHIP) can occur with ageing in healthy individuals. The age distribution and variant allele frequency can be checked in gnomAD to help ascertain whether reported variants may be somatic.

For copy number variants affecting single genes that are being classified using SNV guidelines, PM2_mod can be applied where the variant is absent from gnomAD SV v4.1 and gnomAD CNV v4.1 (if CNV affects 3 or more contiguous exons) or absent from gnomAD SV v4.1 only (if less than 3 contiguous exons). PM2_sup can be applied where it is not absent but is below the defined frequency. Note that for similar-sized CNVs, or those with similar predicted effect (particularly for overlapping in-frame CNVs), overrepresentation in control datasets of variants with a similar predicted effect could support benignity

PM2 should not be applied:

- If all the other evidence for a variant suggests it is likely benign and application of PM2 would move it into the VUS category.
- For areas of the genome with low coverage (<50,000 individuals)
- For certain variant types (e.g. larger or complex indels for example sub-exonic CNVs >50bp, repeat expansion/contractions) which are less readily identified by short-read sequencing.

PM3 – For recessive disorders, detected *in trans* with a pathogenic variant

A points-based system has been developed by the ClinGen Sequence Variant Interpretation group [SVI Recommendation for in trans Criterion \(PM3\)](#). PM3 can be used for the current case being assessed (and tallied with other cases) if the patient is compound heterozygous and the other variant is (likely) pathogenic. The system

also includes scoring for homozygous variants; we recommend application of the points regardless of the class of the homozygous variant or whether parental testing has taken place to confirm homozygosity (the vast majority of variants will now be identified in the context of NGS assays for which allele drop-out is not a significant risk). Points for homozygous variants are capped at a maximum of 1 point (PM3_mod).

It is acceptable to confirm phase by direct testing of e.g. parental samples, or by using proxy methods (for example, apparent linkage to parentally informative SNPs on NGS reads).

For two rare coding variants observed in gnomAD, it is possible to estimate the likelihood that they are in *cis* (on the same allele), see <https://gnomad.broadinstitute.org/variant-cooccurrence>. PM3 should not be applied at any level in the context of two variants that predominantly co-occur; unless testing has confirmed they are *in trans*.

For autosomal recessive disorders it is recommended to count rare cases using PM3 where possible, rather than PS4. For common recessive variants where PM2 is not applicable, see PS4.

PM4 – Protein length changes as a result of in-frame deletions/insertions in a non-repeat region or stop-loss variants

This criterion is used for in-frame deletions or insertions within an exon. Caution is recommended for single amino acid in-frame deletions or insertions where this criterion may be used at a supporting level unless there is gene-specific evidence to warrant use at a moderate level. Selected evolutionary conservation *in silico* predictions tools (e.g. VEST-indel, MutPred-Indel, PROVEAN, Ensembl VEP and BayesDel (18)) can be useful to assess conservation and confirm whether PM4 is applicable. If the region does not show evolutionary conservation PM4 should not be used.

PM4 should be used for truncating variants in the last exon of a gene causing a gain-of-function effect e.g. *SRCAP*, *NOTCH2* (2) and can be upgraded to strong in genes where this mechanism is well-established.

PVS1 should be used for exon-scale deletions and duplications (including single exon).

Please note that PM4 should not be applied if PVS1 is used.

PM5 – Missense change at amino acid residue where a different missense change determined to be pathogenic has been seen before

Where the previously identified missense variant is classified as likely pathogenic and only identified in a single case, we recommend cautious application of this criterion at supporting level only.

The variant being assessed should have a similar or greater predicted impact on the protein than the reference variant. This should be assessed using REVEL score, Grantham distance or BLOSUM62 score.

Where an in-frame deletion or duplication (using the PM4 criterion) overlaps one or more residues in which a known pathogenic or likely pathogenic change has been identified, application of PM5 is reasonable using similar principles. Caution should be applied where the functional consequences of the two variants may reasonably be assumed to be different, and/or where a gain-of-function mechanism may be expected.

PM5 can also be used for non-coding variants where other variants affecting the motif have been previously reported with same predicted impact e.g. creation of new uAUG start codon, disruption of existing uORF, disruption of transcription factor binding site or deletion of core promoter sequence. To visualise the consequence of 5'UTR variants see <https://vutr.rarediseasegenomics.org/>.

Multiple VCEPs (particularly cancer and immunology) allow use of PM5 for PTCs where other pathogenic truncating variants are found in the same region – see ACGS and CanVIG websites for approved VCEP guidelines.

Do not use the same evidence to apply PM1 and PM5, but the two codes can be used together if each supported by independent evidence.

PM6 - Assumed *de novo*, but without confirmation of paternity and maternity

See ClinGen SVI group points-based table as referenced in PS2.

PP1 – Co-segregation with disease in multiple affected family members in a gene definitively known to cause the disease

Co-segregation data can be used for autosomal dominant, autosomal recessive, X-linked and imprinted disorders.

The thresholds suggested by Jarvik and Browning(19) should be used. It is important to consider the number of meioses, **not** the number of informative individuals. Incomplete penetrance, age of onset and phenocopy rates can be incorporated within the calculation. Note that the level of evidence is increased if there are individuals from

multiple unrelated families and the number of informative meioses is summed across the families. For example, a supporting level of evidence could be provided either from a single family with three informative meioses or two families each with one informative meiosis or one family with two informative meioses plus an additional family with one informative meiosis.

In an autosomal recessive disorder where the proband and their sibling is homozygous for a variant and there is a second family where the proband and their sibling are compound heterozygous for the same variant as the first family and a second variant, the segregation information can be combined from both families. However, since co-segregation relates to the allele, the segregation in the second family can only be scored as $\frac{1}{2}$. The information from this scenario would therefore be applied at moderate: $\frac{1}{4} \times \frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{8}$ (>1 family). PP1_supporting can be applied for two families where the proband and their sibling are compound heterozygous and each family is heterozygous for a shared variant: $\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{4}$ (>1 family). Information from unaffected siblings who are not homozygous for the variant can also be incorporated in the calculation, the probability that an unaffected individual is not homozygous is $1 - \frac{1}{4} = \frac{3}{4}$. Segregation information in autosomal recessive conditions cannot be used where only information about the proband in additional families is known, however this information can be used to apply PM3.

Caution should be applied to avoid double-counting if using both PP1 and PP4 together as both implicate pathogenicity of that locus. Biesecker *et al* (20) recommend capping at maximum 5 points for both criteria e.g. PP1_str and PP4_sup

PP2 – Missense variant in a gene that has a low rate of benign missense variation and in which missense variants are a common mechanism of disease

ExAC constraint scores have previously been used as evidence for a low rate of benign variation (21) with Z scores ≥ 3.09 considered significant. The missense constraint score from gnomAD v4.1 should now be used (Z score ≥ 3.09). However, it is important to consider that there is some evidence for constraint for the region encompassing the variant, not just across the entire gene. PP2 should not be used if there is direct evidence that the local region is not under strong selective constraint. Equally, it is reasonable to apply PP2 where there is compelling evidence of local constraint (e.g. local constraint metrics published in gnomAD or DECIPHER (22, 23)) and lack of global constraint (e.g. a Z-score of less than 3.09 for the whole gene), however, care must be taken not to also use this evidence to contribute to PM1 (double-counting).

The DECIPHER database shows regional constraint within the protein view missense constraint track. Havrilla *et al* (24) developed a map of constrained coding regions (CCRs) available as a BED file from <https://github.com/quinlan-lab/ccrhtml> and online browser tool <https://s3.us-east-2.amazonaws.com/ccrs/ccr.ht>. The MetaDome web server <https://stuart.radboudumc.nl/metadome/> also provides a regional tolerance landscape for proteins, as well as annotation of potentially pathogenic variants in paralogous domains in related proteins in ClinVar. Note that it is not appropriate to use PP2 and consequently classify a variant as being of uncertain significance in the scenario that the allele frequency data within gnomAD would classify as likely benign or benign.

Avoid double-counting evidence for constraint in both PM1 and PP2.

PP3 – Computational evidence supports a deleterious effect on the gene or gene product (conservation, evolutionary, splicing impact, etc.)

Evidence-based ClinGen approved threshold scores for missense *in silico* tools have been established and aligned to ACMG evidence strengths ranging from supporting, moderate and strong for PP3(16). However, based on our impact assessment (Supplementary data S5) and decision to not downgrade PM2, **we recommend use of PP3 at supporting strength only** pending ACMG v4.0 guidelines i.e. variants should not be classified as likely pathogenic based on *in silico* (PP3_str) and rarity (PM2_mod) alone.

To predict the impact of missense variants, it is recommended that a single tool is used to avoid introducing bias(16). Meta-predictor tools (e.g. REVEL (25) or BayesDel (26)) have been shown to have high positive and negative predictive values and outperform other tools (16, 27, 28). REVEL scores are commonly used in the UK and we recommend adopting the ClinGen lowest threshold only i.e. apply PP3_supporting for variants with score ≥ 0.644 (16). However, REVEL does not perform well for all genes e.g. *PKD1*, *DSG2* and genes where the mechanism is gain-of-function (personal communications from ACGS laboratories and ClinGen). A new tool, AlphaMissense, combines structural information from AlphaFold with evolutionary conservation and achieves high auROC compared with other tools (29). For genes where REVEL is known not to perform well, or the REVEL score is borderline other high performing tools such as BayesDel (threshold >0.13) or AlphaMissense (threshold >0.792) (30) may be used as an alternative.

PP3 can be used for non-canonical splicing variants. For canonical splice variants see PVS1.

In silico splicing prediction tools can be used as evidence to suggest a significant impact on splicing potential for splice site variants. SpliceAI (<https://spliceailookup.broadinstitute.org/>) using the recommended delta score threshold of >0.2 is a highly accurate single splice prediction tool (2, 31). Note that many commonly used splice prediction tools (such as MaxEntScan, NNsplice and GeneSplicer) have no predictive power for GC-donor splice

sites and minor spliceosome (U12) introns; tools such as SpliceAI and SpliceSiteFinderLike are more appropriate alternatives. To detect all predicted splicing events, we recommend using SpliceAI with an expanded window of 5Kbp-10Kbp (see PVS1).

Variants affecting the last nucleotide of an exon (if G to non-G) or +5G have an increased prior probability of aberrant splicing (32).

PVS1(RNA) should be used if mRNA analysis is undertaken and demonstrates the presence of an abnormal transcript(s) predicted to result in loss of protein expression. In this situation PP3 would not apply as well since the splice prediction is not independent evidence.

PP4 – Patient’s phenotype or family history is highly specific for a disease with a single genetic aetiology

This evidence criterion incorporates the prior probability that a patient will have a pathogenic variant in a particular gene or genes and therefore does not need to be limited to diseases where there is a single genetic aetiology. This criterion may also be applied in the scenario where a patient has a rare combination of clinical features for which there are a very limited number of known genetic aetiologies, and all those genes have been tested. Non-specific phenotypes such as intellectual disability, seizure disorder without a specific EEG pattern and subtle abnormalities of the corpus callosum should never be used in isolation as evidence for PP4. Caution should be exercised when considering phenotypic features which are specific to a disorder that is genetically heterogeneous.

The testing strategy used to identify the variant is also important. For example, when a single gene test has been undertaken because the patient’s phenotype is a “good fit” for that specific genetic aetiology, there is a high prior probability that a variant identified within that gene will be causative of the patient’s disease and the test specificity is high. In contrast, when a large panel test for a genetically heterogeneous condition is performed, the overall prior probability for finding a causative variant is the sum of the prior probabilities for each individual gene. Using a gene-agnostic whole exome or genome sequencing strategy with variant filtering by mode of inheritance provides significantly increased specificity compared to a gene panel approach and can be cited as additional evidence.

In some situations, it is considered appropriate to use this evidence criterion at a moderate or strong level after MDT discussion (see below and Supplementary Table S4 for examples). To use PP4 it is essential that a test has been performed which will identify the majority of known genetic causes of the condition in question.

The specificity of a phenotype may be supported by the presence of a specific constellation of recognisable clinical features consistent with the genetic finding, for example facial gestalt and severe global developmental delay/intellectual disability in a patient with a *NIPBL* variant. Where additional more specific phenotypic features are present this can be used as a moderate piece of evidence (e.g. one of the following additional features; upper-limb reduction defects, growth retardation and microcephaly).

Circumstances where PP4 might be used as a strong piece of evidence include where there is a response to a drug treatment, enzyme activity assay, specific blood indices, methylation signature or muscle biopsy analysis that is pathognomonic of a specific genetic cause of a disorder and would in the absence of genetic confirmation be considered a diagnostic finding.

See CanVIG *BRCA1/BRCA2* guidelines for incorporation of ENIGMA’s multifactorial evidence likelihood ratios using PP4 at variable strengths.

PP4 and PS4 can be applied for the same cases providing that the phenotype is confirmed and all known genes related to that phenotype have been tested.

BA1 – Allele frequency is above 5%

This can be used as stand-alone evidence of benign impact. For the majority of rare diseases, the Richards *et al* (13) threshold of 5% is very high and a more accurate % can be calculated for specific genes using the Cardiodb tool (see BS1) applying disease prevalence, penetrance and genetic heterogeneity, with the allelic heterogeneity fixed at 1.

Used for intragenic CNVs with frequency >1% involving an autosomal dominant disorder with high penetrance. See CNV guidelines for section covering 2F + 2G and 2C-2G (Supplementary Table S2).

BS1 – Allele frequency is greater than expected for disorder

A very useful tool is available to determine whether the allele frequency of the variant is greater than expected for the disorder (17). In the absence of precise information about the disease prevalence and penetrance we recommend using conservative settings (by selecting the highest likely prevalence and the lowest likely penetrance) to see if the variant frequency on the gnomAD database exceeds the maximum credible allele frequency. The tool can be accessed at <http://cardiodb.org/allelefrequencyapp/>.

For an autosomal dominant disorder with high penetrance, it is acceptable to use BS1_Strong as stand-alone evidence to classify a variant as likely benign.

Caution should be applied for variants in gnomAD v2 with quality flags, use of the latest gnomAD dataset (v4.1) is recommended for any regions that show poor genotyping quality, low average read depth and/or that reside in gene regions with known pseudogenes or paralogs (e.g. *TUBB2B*, *PRSS1*).

Can be used at strong for intragenic CNVs with frequency >0.5% involving an autosomal dominant disorder with high penetrance; for rare CNVs apply at supporting. See CNV guidelines supplementary table S2 for section covering 4O.

BS2 – Observed in a healthy adult individual for a recessive (homozygous), dominant (heterozygous), or X-linked (hemizygous) disorder with full penetrance expected at an early age

Use scientific judgement depending on mode of inheritance, age of onset and disease penetrance.

For example, for a highly penetrant dominant disease BS2 can be used for ≥ 2 heterozygous healthy (appropriately phenotyped) individuals or ≥ 2 homozygotes in gnomAD where biallelic phenotype is predicted to be severe and paediatric onset.

In recessive disorders, BS2 can be used for ≥ 2 appropriately phenotyped healthy homozygotes. Incidence in gnomAD (phenotype unknown) can also be used for recessive diseases with severe paediatric onset.

For disorders with later age of onset or variable penetrance, a higher number of healthy individuals and/or more detailed phenotyping is required.

BS1 and BS2 can be used together to score a variant as benign.

BS3 - Well-established in vitro or in vivo functional studies show no damaging effect on protein function

For protein assays only. For RNA splicing assays see BP7(RNA).

Weighting of BS3 should be determined according to assay criteria defined by Brnich *et al*(14).

BS3 should not be applied for an assay of protein function when *in silico* tools predict effect on splicing and/or the variant is located at the first or last three bases of the exon.

BS4 - Non-segregation with disease

See Jarvik and Browning(19). Care should be taken to ensure the phenotype of other affected family members is consistent with proband, and that the disorder does not have common phenocopies e.g. breast cancer, hearing loss etc.

BP1 – Missense variant in a gene for which primarily truncating variants are known to cause disease

This criterion is used for missense variants in non-conserved regions of the gene where the mechanism of disease is primarily truncating variants e.g. *APC*-related familial adenomatous polyposis.

It can also be used for loss of function variants in a gene where the disease is caused by gain of function variants or dominant negative loss of function variants (e.g. those in the last exon of a gene) where there is no evidence of a loss-of-function mechanism and where the gene is not constrained against loss-of-function variation in an appropriate control population (e.g. gnomAD).

It may also be used for missense variants, which do not affect splicing, in genes where missense variants are known to cluster only in key functional domains and the variant of interest is outside these domains e.g. *BRCA1* and *BRCA2*.

BP2 - Observed *in trans* (on different alleles) with a pathogenic variant for a fully penetrant dominant gene/disorder; or observed *in cis* (same allele) with a pathogenic variant in any inheritance pattern

To be applied for affected cases where a pathogenic variant in a fully penetrant dominant gene that explains the clinical phenotype has been identified. If biallelic variants in that gene cause a different clinical phenotype, the patient must be at an appropriate age at which biallelic pathogenic variants would be anticipated to be penetrant for that phenotype and/or the patient has been clinically assessed to exclude relevant phenotype.

BP3 - In-frame deletions/insertions in a repetitive region without a known function

Assess nucleotide and protein conservation, function of region and variant frequency in population controls. Use of *in silico* tools MutPredIndel, VEST-indel, PROVEAN etc may also help with application.

BP4 – Multiple lines of computational evidence suggest no impact on gene or gene product

We recommend use of BP4 for missense variants with REVEL score ≤ 0.290 .

For splicing variants, Splice AI delta score ≤ 0.1

This criterion should not be used when there is evidence that *in silico* tools do not show satisfactory performance for prediction of pathogenic variants in that gene.

BP4 should not be applied for splicing variants where RNA evidence has already been used in BP7(RNA).

BP5 - Variant found in a case with an alternate molecular basis for disease

Caution should be exercised for genes in which co-occurrence of pathogenic variants is reported with no/little impact on clinical phenotype e.g. *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* pathogenic variants can co-occur and do not show any significant impact on cancer type or age of onset.

Caution should also be exercised if the PV identified does not explain all the clinical features or if the patient has a blended phenotype incorporating elements of both genetic diagnoses.

BP7 – A synonymous (silent) variant for which splicing prediction algorithms predict no impact to the splice consensus sequence nor the creation of a new splice site AND the nucleotide is not highly conserved; splice variants where RNA studies have confirmed no impact

BP7 can also be used for intronic variants at or beyond +7/-21 (where BP4 is also applicable), and non-coding variants in UTRs.

Synonymous variants with no predicted effect on splicing and the nucleotide is not highly conserved can be classified as likely benign using BP4 and BP7.

Not highly conserved regions are those with e.g. PhyloP score < 0.1 .

ClinGen Splicing SVI group recommend use of BP7 (RNA) for intronic variants and synonymous variants shown to have no effect on splicing by RNA studies. When a substitution is confirmed to have no impact on splicing by a suitable *in vitro* assay, BP7 can be upweighted to BP7_Strong (RNA).

Supplementary Table S2: Additional information for section usage in CNV guidelines to supplement ACMG/ClinGen guidelines

Please note that the Tables referred to in brackets relate to the Tables in Riggs-Rooney et al 2020(33)

Section 1: Initial assessment of genomic content:

This section determines whether the CNV contains protein-coding genes or known functionally important elements.

1A (Table 1 and Table 2)

Contains protein-coding genes or known functionally important elements

If only one gene is relevant for the patient phenotype, then use of SNV guidelines may be more appropriate

1A (default points = 0): If the CNV contains protein-coding genes, continue with your evaluation. If the CNV does not contain any protein-coding genes*, and is not overlapping population CNVs, it is important to consider the possibility that it contains a functionally important element (which could be a non-coding RNA). If the upstream or downstream flanking genes are within ~1Mb and are associated with a highly specific phenotype which relates to the patient's phenotype, perform a literature search to determine if the region contains a functionally important element for that gene/s (e.g. CNVs within 1Mb of SHH, SOX, HOX and FOX gene families have been reported in the literature). If evidence is found, a classification of likely pathogenic (0.90) can be applied based on the strength of the literature evidence and professional judgement. For some CNVs the SNV guidelines may be more applicable.

*DECIPHER can be used to list all genes within a CNV and the list can be filtered to display 'protein coding genes' and 'disease-associated genes'.

1B (Table 1 and Table 2)

Does NOT contain protein-coding or any known functionally important elements

1B (default points = -0.60): Depending on the method used to detect the CNV, it is important to consider all genes in the maximum breakpoint interval for clinical relevance. If the CNV minimum and maximum interval is intronic but the gene is associated with a highly specific phenotype that fits the patient's clinical presentation and there is literature evidence to suggest the intron is important, then continue with your evaluation.

Section 2: Overlap with Established (or Predicted) Pathogenic or Benign Dosage Sensitive Genes/Genomic Regions:

In this section, the CNV is evaluated for overlap with established dosage sensitive genes or genomic regions or established benign genes or genomic regions (*skip to Section 3 if your CNV does not overlap an established HI/TS gene/region*)

If a score of ≥ 0.99 (Pathogenic) or ≥ -0.99 (Benign) is reached in this section, application of subsequent sections is not required

Various curations are used to help determine if a gene/region is dosage sensitive (https://www.clinicalgenome.org/site/assets/files/6428/dosage_sop-scoring-1.pdf, <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/gene2phenotype>, https://clinicalgenome.org/site/assets/files/5391/version_9_gene_curation_sop_final2.pdf).

To be considered an established pathogenic dosage sensitive gene/region it will have one or more of the below:

- ClinGen Dosage Sensitivity haploinsufficiency (HI) score of 3 ('sufficient evidence')
- Monoallelic Gene2Phenotype (G2P) gene with a 'definitive' status and 'absent gene product' as the consequence
- Biallelic G2P gene with a 'definitive' status and 'absent gene product' as the consequence
- Gene-Disease Validity (ClinGen) with a 'definitive' status and sufficient evidence of predicted or proven null variants to show loss-of-function is a disease mechanism (either AD or AR genes)
- ClinGen Dosage sensitivity triplosensitivity (TS) score of 3 ('sufficient evidence')

Section 2 can be applied at reduced points to a gene/region with one or more of the below:

- ClinGen Dosage Sensitivity haploinsufficiency (HI) or triplosensitivity score of 2 ('emerging evidence')
- Monoallelic Gene2Phenotype (G2P) gene with a 'strong' status and 'absent gene product' as the consequence
- Biallelic G2P gene with a 'strong' status and 'absent gene product' as the consequence
- Gene-Disease Validity (ClinGen) with a 'strong' status and sufficient evidence of predicted or proven null variants to show loss-of-function is a disease mechanism (either AD or AR genes).

In general, if the gene/region has already been curated as above, it is not essential to perform a formal curation (like the framework developed by Strande *et al* (3) but laboratories are expected to ensure that the evidence provided for the curations was sufficient for the gene/disease association and that loss-of-function or triplosensitivity is the mechanism of disease. Please see caveats for curations in PVS1.

To be considered an established benign gene/region it will have one or more of the below:

- ClinGen Dosage sensitivity score of 40 ('dosage sensitivity unlikely')

- Commonly seen CNV within cohort that has a platform frequency of >1%
- A frequency >1% on the DGV gold standard dataset or gnomAD SV dataset

When using reported frequency from population databases you must consider the size/number of alleles examined within the study/s used. Some frequencies can be skewed if the variant was only examined in a small proportion of cases. As a general rule, it is recommended that frequency calculations are based on a minimum of 10,000 alleles/5000 samples. The gnomAD SV v4.1 dataset contains 63,046 genomes; the sample size of studies used in the DGV database can be found here: http://dgv.tcag.ca/dgv/app/search?ref=GRCh37/hg19#tabs-view_all_information_study

2A + 2B (Table 1 and Table 2) and 2H (Table 2)

Complete overlap with an established HI/LOF or TS gene/region + partial overlap of an established HI/LOF or TS region

2A (default points = 1.00; range 0.90 to 1.00): CNVs completely containing established dosage sensitive genes/regions are a pathogenic classification (1.00 points) and do not require any further evidence to be gathered; however, you may still need to investigate the clinical implications of the CNV and its association with your patient's phenotype/management for the report.

- For CNVs completely containing a dosage sensitive gene/region with a ClinGen HI/TS score of 2, a monoallelic/biallelic G2P gene with a 'strong' status and 'absent gene product' as the consequence, or a gene with a Gene-Disease Validity (ClinGen) with a 'strong' status and sufficient evidence of predicted or proven null variants to show loss-of-function is a disease mechanism, apply 2A at 0.90 points.

2B (default points = 0): CNVs that partially overlap established dosage sensitive regions where the critical gene/region has not yet been established require further investigations.

2H (Table 2) (default points = 0): An established HI/LOF gene that is fully contained within a duplication should not be presumed to be disease-causing unless the gene is also known to be associated with a triplosensitive disorder.

2C – 2D (Table 1) and 2J – 2L (Table 2) and 2E (Table 1) and 2I (Table 2)

**Partial overlap with a gene (one breakpoint is within the gene and the other not)
Intragenic del/dup within a HI/LOF gene (both breakpoints within the gene)**

SNV guidelines are recommended for these variants.

2H (Table 1)

≥2 HI predictors suggest at least 1 gene in the interval is HI

If only one gene is relevant for the patient phenotype, then use of SNV guidelines may be more appropriate.

2H (default points = 0.15): Predictive *in silico* scores for HI of genes can be found on the DECIPHER database under the gene entry.

Common HI predictors that can be applied to this category include:

- pLI, LOEUF, sHET and pHaplo (definitions, thresholds + information can be found on DECIPHER)
 - please note that pLI and LOEUF use the same gnomAD data but presented differently and should not be used together.
 - %HI scores have been removed from DECIPHER and been replaced by pHaplo.

Do not use for deletions that involve an established HI/LOF gene (i.e. if you have already applied categories 2A-2B, Table 1). The points associated with 2H should only be given once; do not count this piece of evidence multiple times, even if there is more than one gene in the region predicted to be HI.

2F + 2G (Table 1) and 2C-2G (Table 2)

Identical or completely contained within or overlaps with an established benign region

2F (Table 1); 2C, 2D, and 2F (Table 2) (default points = -1.00): When a CNV under evaluation is contained completely within an established benign region or is larger but contains no additional genes.

- If your CNV is a partially overlapping gene duplication you cannot use established benign regions that encompass the whole of that gene in your evaluation. The expected potential impact of intragenic or partial gains is different to that of a whole gene duplication. In such situations it may be more applicable to compare your CNV to established benign copy number losses.
- Be aware that some autosomal recessive variants could have a population frequency >1% and should not be interpreted as benign based solely on their frequency.

2G (Table 1 and Table 2) (default points = 0): If the CNV only overlaps the benign region, or is larger, and contains additional genes, you must continue your evaluation to determine if the region contains any clinically relevant genes or functionally important elements.

Section 3: Evaluation of Gene Number

This section evaluates the number of protein coding genes involved in the CNV.

3A – 3C (Table 1 and Table 2)

The number of genes wholly or partially involved in the CNV

In general, when a CNV contains a very large number of genes, it becomes more likely that loss or gain of this amount of genetic material will result in some demonstrable phenotypic consequence. However, the exact nature of the phenotypic effect cannot be determined based on gene number alone.

3A (default points = 0): Deletions containing less than 24 genes and duplications containing less than 34 genes.

3B (default points = 0.45): Deletions containing between 25 and 34 genes, or duplications containing between 35-49 genes.

3C (default points = 0.90): Deletions containing 35 or more genes, or duplications containing 50 or more genes.

Caution should be applied if the CNV involves clusters of genes or gene families, particularly those that are non-coding or lack any known clinical association. Each cluster/family should be counted as a single gene. If a gene within a cluster/gene family has a disease-association, count them as an individual gene.

Section 4: Detailed Evaluation of Genomic Content Using Cases from Published Literature, Public Databases, and/or Internal Laboratory Data

In this section evidence is gathered of comparable cases in the literature and databases to support or refute the clinical significance of the gene/genomic region under evaluation (*skip this section if Section 2 has been applied i.e. if your CNV contained a curated HI/TS gene/region*).

If you have reached a score of ≥ 0.99 (Pathogenic) or ≥ -0.99 (Benign) you can skip this section.

The nature of CNVs mean that their evaluation often requires the assessment of both genes of known and unknown clinical significance. Many CNVs will not overlap *established* dosage sensitive or benign genes/regions. These CNVs require evaluation using the literature and databases to establish if a similar CNV has been reported in another proband/family and whether or not the CNV has a clinical association.

Section 4 (Table 1 and Table 2) is split into two evidence types:

1. **Individual Case Evidence (4A-4K)**
2. **Case-Control or General Population Data (4L-4O)**

1. **Individual Case Evidence**

4A – 4E (Table 1 and Table 2)

Assessment of the literature and databases for similar CNVs to your region of interest

4A-4C: Evaluates *de novo* case evidence by determining how consistent the reported phenotype in the similar case/s is to what is expected for that gene/region, how specific that phenotype is, how unique it is to the gene/region, and whether the *de novo* status is confirmed or assumed.

Cases in the literature/databases with highly specific, well-defined phenotypes, that have been confirmed to have arisen *de novo* (e.g. trio genome sequencing has been undertaken – which will confirm maternity and paternity), represent the strongest evidence. The less specific the reported phenotype is, the less certain you can be that it is related to your gene/region of interest and not to other genes/factors. Also, assumed *de novo* (e.g. parents tested on microarray) is associated with fewer points consistent with the approach taken in the SNV guidelines.

“Highly specific, well-defined” phenotypes have a distinct and known genetic aetiology with limited genetic heterogeneity. “Non-specific” phenotypes are those that may be more common, have more considerable genetic heterogeneity, and/or can be caused by aetiologies other than genetic variation.

Phenotype	Examples
Highly specific, relatively unique to the gene/region	Fixed dilated pupils (Gillespie syndrome) Fetal adrenocortical cytomegaly (Beckwith-Wiedemann syndrome) Specific scan findings, biochemical assay results etc
Highly specific, not necessarily unique to the gene/region	Leukodystrophy Metopic ridging Skeletal dysplasias EIEE (not simply ‘seizures’ or ‘epilepsy’) Constellation of findings like coloboma, heart defects, choanal atresia, growth delays, genital anomalies, and ear abnormalities associated with CHARGE syndrome
Not highly specific, and/or with high genetic heterogeneity	Intellectual disability Developmental delay Autism

Functional studies (e.g. *in vitro* or *in vivo* animal model studies, biochemical assays, or scan findings etc) may support the specificity of the reported phenotype and therefore determine which evidence category to use; they should not be used to upgrade the points value for a particular category.

A range of points is provided for 4A-4C. Use the default number of points for each case or none at all if the evidence is weak. For example:

- **4A** will be either 0.45 (confirmed *de novo*) or 0.30 (assumed *de novo*)
- **4B** will be either 0.30 (confirmed *de novo*) or 0.15 (assumed *de novo*)
- **4C** will be either 0.15 (confirmed *de novo*) or 0.10 (assumed *de novo*)

Note that the maximum total score you can reach using evidence from cases that 4A – 4C is applicable to is 0.90.

4D (default points = 0; range = 0 to -0.30): For *de novo* cases in which the reported phenotype is either not consistent with what is expected for a given gene/region, or simply not consistent in general, the recommended points applied is 0.

- For negative points to be applied to cases using 4D, clinical judgement should be used to determine if there is strong enough evidence of inconsistency in phenotypes across the cases and if appropriate phenotyping has been undertaken and if the cases are comparable. However, it is unlikely that sufficient evidence will be found to award negative points.
- If evidence is found, apply -0.15 points to each case.

Note that the maximum score you can reach using evidence from cases that 4D is applicable to is -0.30.

4E (default points = 0.10; max. total = 0.30): For cases where the inheritance is unknown, points can only be applied to each case if the phenotype is *highly specific* and consistent with that expected for the gene/region.

Genes of unknown clinical significance: When the gene(s) being assessed are of unknown clinical significance there must be at least two *de novo* cases with similar phenotypes before points can be assigned (i.e. the two cases count as one piece of evidence/case). Each additional case observed with a consistent phenotype may be awarded additional points. If only a single *de novo* case has been reported in the literature/databases, and the variant under evaluation by the laboratory is *de novo* with a phenotype consistent with the phenotype of the single reported case, then both cases can be used together as a single piece of evidence and the appropriate category can be applied. In this scenario, additional points should not be assigned to your case in Section 5.

- Use the points values from 4A – 4C for your evidence. For example, if the similar phenotype is highly specific and confirmed *de novo* status, 0.45 points is applicable; if the similar phenotype is non-specific and the cases are assumed *de novo* then only 0.10 points is applicable.

4F – 4K (Table 1 and Table 2)

Assesses the segregation of the similar CNV within families in the literature and databases.

Segregation of a variant among similarly affected family members can lend support to the argument that the variant may be disease-causing. Instances in which the variant appears not to segregate with affected status does not automatically mean it is not disease-causing.

4F-4H: Covers segregation among similarly affected family members. The CNV guidelines adopt a conservative approach to segregation because segregation implicates a locus, and not necessarily a particular gene or variant, and because of the difficulty in determining whether CNVs reported in the literature/databases are the same given the variability in the accuracy of breakpoints depending on the technology used. Therefore at least 3 documented segregations among affected individuals are required to assign any points:

- **4F** (default points = 0.15): 3-4 segregations
- **4G** (default points = 0.30): 5-6 segregations
- **4H** (default points = 0.45): 7 or more segregations

Only those individuals with both the genotype and the phenotype, or individuals who are obligate carriers, can be counted as evidence. Segregations can be added across families. When counting segregations, the proband is not counted:

- # of segregations = (# of genotype/phenotype positive) – 1

Caution should be applied when using large families for segregation analysis. The maximum number of points allocated to CNV segregation from the literature and databases is 0.45. The guidelines aim to avoid situations where a CNV could reach a likely pathogenic/pathogenic classification by simply using evidence of segregation from one family. The goal is to try and collect as many diverse pieces of information as possible to determine the classification of the variant. However, for some variants this is not possible, and if there is substantial segregation evidence, overriding the maximum points could be considered (e.g., well-studied gene with definitive gene-disease association and numerous unrelated families with documented segregation).

Please note:

The CNV guidelines separate literature/database segregation (Section 4F-4H) from your case segregation (Section 5D), whereas the SNV guidelines incorporate them together. Points collated for segregation evidence gathered from both sections can be used towards the classification of the variant to a combined maximum of 0.45 points.

4I (default points = -0.45; max. total = -0.90): Apparent non-segregations include instances in which another *affected* individual in the case family is found *not* to have the variant in question. Assign the default number of negative points when the individuals in the family are affected with similar, *highly specific* phenotypes (with no known phenocopies) and are not found to carry the same variant.

- Consider downgrading this evidence to -0.15 (supporting) when phenocopies are a possibility.

4J and 4K: Instances in which an *unaffected* individual *is* found to have the variant in question, the specificity of the phenotype in the affected family member/s plays a role in how many points can be applied.

- **4J** (default points = -0.30; max. total = -0.90): specific, well-defined phenotype
- **4K** (default points = -0.15; max. total = -0.30): nonspecific phenotype

Consider whether the family member found to have the variant is truly unaffected. Do not assign negative points if there's a plausible explanation why the phenotype may not be present/observed/reported (e.g. known incomplete or age-related penetrance, clinical feature not readily observable, individual not properly evaluated, variable expressivity), or if the family member is simply stated in a publication/database not to be affected, but no details of their evaluation are provided. If the individual has been clinically phenotyped or tested for the particular phenotypic feature (e.g. by radiological investigation or biochemical assay), and there is no evidence of the phenotype, assign the default number of negative points. Note that phenotypes segregating in a family may exhibit variable expressivity but may still be part of the same phenotypic spectrum (e.g. autism spectrum disorder, intellectual disability, seizures, and schizophrenia observed in different individuals may all be caused by the same CNV as part of the developmental brain disorder spectrum).

2. Case-Control or General Population Data

4L, 4M, 4N (Table 1 & Table 2)

CNV has been studied as part of a case-control study

If the CNV has been studied as part of a well-powered case-control study, points may be added or deducted based on enrichment (or lack thereof) in the clinical population. Interpretation of case-control data should include evaluation of significance (i.e. p-value), effect size (e.g. likelihood ratio), and clinical information (e.g. phenotypic specificity). CNVs in this category will be observed at a significantly higher frequency in cases versus controls ($p \leq 0.05$), and with a strong effect size (odds ratio or likelihood ratio >5) and relatively narrow associated 95% confidence interval (lower bound >1).

CNVs with the highest points values will be observed in association with a consistent, specific, well-defined phenotype (0.45 points, **4L**). Those lacking phenotypic specificity, but enriched, can also be counted (0.30 points, **4M**). CNVs that are not enriched and are observed at similar (or higher) frequencies in controls compared to cases, can be deducted points (-0.90 points, **4N**).

Case-control study data is rarely available for rare diseases. However, in-house datasets (case cohort) and the gnomADSV v4.1 and gnomADCNV v4.1 datasets (control cohort) can be used to calculate a p-value using https://www.medcalc.org/calc/odds_ratio.php to allow 4L to be applied at reduced points if the variant has been identified in multiple (two or more) unrelated affected individuals (with a consistent, rare, well-defined phenotype). It is acceptable to apply 4L at 0.30 if the variant has a p-value of ≤ 0.05 and at 0.15 points if the variant has a p-value of ≤ 0.1 . Case-control data ideally needs to be from equivalent ethnic groups.

4O (Table 1 & Table 2)

CNV is present in population databases

4O (default points = -1.00; range = 0 to -1.00): This category covers CNVs that involve regions seen in population databases. There is overlap between the evidence that can be used for categories 4O and that used for 2F (Table 1) and 2C, 2D, and 2F (Table 2) for established benign variants (frequency $>1\%$). Category 4O is used for variants that are present at a frequency less than 1%:

Frequency	Points
$>0.5\%$	-0.90
0.1-0.5%	-0.30
0.01-0.09%	-0.15

Section 5: Evaluation of Inheritance Pattern/Family History for your Patient

This section evaluates the inheritance and family history of the CNV being studied

Your patient's phenotype is incorporated into Section 5, which covers the inheritance pattern/family history for your case. The points assigned to inheritance information in this section (*de novo*, inherited from an unaffected family member, inherited from an affected family member) is modified by the specificity of your patient's phenotype. The points-metric is based around how specific and well-defined the patient's phenotype is in relation to the gene/region

in question and follows the principles laid out in Section 4; highly specific, well-defined phenotypes represent stronger evidence and more points than disparate or non-specific phenotypes.

5A (Table 1 and Table 2)

The CNV in your case is found to be de novo

5A: Use the scoring metrics from 4A-4D. If your patient's phenotype is:

- highly specific and relatively unique to the gene/region (~4A)
 - apply 0.45 points (if confirmed *de novo*)
 - apply 0.30 points (if assumed *de novo*)
- consistent with the gene/region, is highly specific but not necessarily unique to the gene/region (~4B)
 - apply 0.30 points (if confirmed *de novo*)
 - apply 0.15 points (if assumed *de novo*)
- consistent with the gene/region, but not highly specific and/or with high genetic heterogeneity (~4C)
 - apply 0.15 points (if confirmed *de novo*)
 - apply 0.10 points (if assumed *de novo*)
- not consistent with the gene/region (~4D)
 - apply 0 points

5B – 5D (Table 1 and Table 2)

The CNV in your case is found to be inherited

5B (default points = -0.30): Apply if your patient's phenotype is *specific and well-defined* and has been inherited from an unaffected parent.

5C (default points = -0.15): Apply if your patient's phenotype is *non-specific* and has been inherited from an unaffected parent.

5D: Use the scoring metrics from 4F-4H. If your patient's CNV is segregating with a consistent phenotype in the family and the number of segregations are:

- 3-4 segregations (~4F)
 - apply 0.15 points
- 5-6 segregations (~4G)
 - apply 0.30 points
- 7 or more segregations (~4H)
 - apply 0.45 points

5E (Table 1 and Table 2)

The CNV in your case is not segregating in the family

5E: Use the scoring metrics from 4I-4K. If your patient's CNV is:

- not found in another family member affected with a consistent, specific, well-defined phenotype (~4I)
 - apply -0.45 points
- found in another family member unaffected with the specific, well-defined phenotype (~4J)
 - apply -0.30 points
- found in another family member unaffected with the non-specific phenotype (~4K)
 - apply -0.15 points

5F – 5H (Table 1 and Table 2)

The inheritance information for the CNV is unknown

If inheritance studies have not been undertaken or are uninformative (e.g. only one parent received), no points are applied (**5F**).

However, if the patient's phenotype in its entirety is consistent with a specific genetic aetiology, points may be assigned (**5G and 5H**). These categories should be considered equivalent to using PP4 in the sequence variant guidelines at supporting or moderate strength.

5G (default points = 0.10, Table 1 and Table 2): Can be applied if your patient's phenotype is non-specific but is consistent with what has been described in other similar cases.

- 5G should not be applied simply because the patient has a non-specific phenotype such as intellectual disability or autism spectrum disorder. Your patient must have multiple non-specific features that are the same as described in other similar cases.

5H (default points = 0.30, Table 1; default points = 0.15 points, Table 2): Can be applied if your patient's phenotype is highly specific and consistent with what has been described in other similar cases.

A range of points exists for 5G and 5H but the default points should always be applied if the evidence is used.

Supplementary Table A: Recommended approach to reporting genomic variants in probands

Note from Richards *et al* (13) that pathogenic is proposed to mean a 99% certainty that the variant is disease-causing and likely pathogenic equates to 90% certainty.

Classification	Variant included in report?	Result summary for genomic laboratory report	Explanatory notes
Pathogenic	Yes	Genetic diagnosis of disorder/syndrome X OR Genetic diagnosis of (syndromic) intellectual disability OR Genetic diagnosis of (“Gene name”) - related disorder OR Confirms a genetic diagnosis of disorder X (if there was clinical suspicion of this specific disorder) OR Pathogenic unbalanced CNV detected	Very high likelihood that the variant is causative of the disorder >99% certainty that the variant is pathogenic

<p>Likely pathogenic</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>Consistent with a genetic diagnosis of disorder/syndrome X</p> <p>OR</p> <p>Consistent with a genetic diagnosis of (syndromic) intellectual disability</p> <p>OR</p> <p>Consistent with a genetic diagnosis of (“Gene name”) - related disorder</p> <p>OR</p> <p>Likely pathogenic CNV detected</p>	<p>High likelihood that the variant is causative of the disorder</p> <p><i>>90% certainty that the variant is pathogenic</i></p>
<p>Uncertain significance*</p> <p><i>VUS where further testing or investigations could be considered as the results have the potential to change the classification to likely pathogenic</i></p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>Variant of uncertain significance identified – consider further action</p> <p><u>Clearly</u> describe in the report the action required that could change the classification to likely pathogenic</p>	<p>Further testing or investigations could be undertaken to re-classify the variant as likely pathogenic.</p> <p>Examples include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) testing parents to determine whether <i>de novo</i> b) mRNA analysis for variants predicted to cause aberrant splicing c) testing affected relatives to show co-segregation d) Clinical assessment and/or investigation(s) to provide phenotypic specificity evidence e) trial of a treatment that is specific for the genetic aetiology f) determining the location and/or orientation of copy number gains

<p>Uncertain significance*</p> <p><i>VUS where no further evidence can be obtained</i></p>	Not usually	<p>A genetic cause for the patient's clinical presentation has not been identified</p> <p>State in the result text that the result does not exclude a genetic diagnosis</p>	<p>These variants should only be reported in exceptional circumstances following MDT discussion (see section 7.1.1).</p>
<p>Uncertain significance*</p> <p><i>VUS where no further evidence can be obtained</i></p>	No	<p>A genetic cause for the patient's clinical presentation has not been identified</p> <p>State in the result text that the result does not exclude a genetic diagnosis</p>	<p>These variants are almost invariably unlikely to be disease-causing and are potentially confusing if included in the report.</p> <p>They should only be reported in exceptional circumstances following MDT discussion (see section 7.1.1).</p>
<p>Likely benign</p>	No	<p>A genetic cause for the patient's clinical presentation has not been identified</p> <p>State in the result text that the result does not exclude a genetic diagnosis</p>	<p>These variants are not relevant and potentially confusing if included in the report</p> <p><i>>90% certainty that the variant is benign</i></p>
<p>Benign</p>	No	<p>A genetic cause for the patient's clinical presentation has not been identified</p> <p>State in the result text that the result does not exclude a genetic diagnosis</p>	<p>These variants are not relevant and potentially confusing if included in the report</p> <p><i>>99.9% certainty that the variant is benign</i></p>
<p><i>Variant previously reported in the literature as (likely) pathogenic but now classified as (likely) benign</i></p>	No	<p>A genetic cause for the patient's clinical presentation has not been identified</p> <p>State in the result text that the result does not exclude a genetic diagnosis</p>	<p>There is no clinical utility in reporting these historical false positive results and potential risk of misinterpretation</p>

<i>A variant type/mechanism that does not fit with the established disease mechanism</i>	No	<p>A genetic cause for the patient’s clinical presentation has not been identified</p> <p>State in the result text that the result does not exclude a genetic diagnosis</p>	For example a loss of function variant in a gene where the disease mechanism is gain of function or is mediated via an effect upon a specific protein structure
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*See Figure 2 for sub-classifications of variants of uncertain significance

Supplementary Table B: Additional recommendations for reporting genomic variants in recessive disorders

Classification	Variant(s) included in report?	Result summary for genomic laboratory report	Explanatory notes
<i>Recessive disorder with two pathogenic variants identified and known to be in trans</i>	Yes	<p>Genetic diagnosis of disorder X</p> <p>OR</p> <p>Genetic diagnosis of (“Gene name”)-related disorder</p> <p>OR</p> <p>Confirms a genetic diagnosis of disorder X (if cases where there was clinical suspicion of this specific disorder)</p>	<p>Very high likelihood that the variants are causative of the disorder</p> <p><i>>99% certainty that each variant is pathogenic</i></p>
<i>Recessive disorder with one pathogenic and one likely pathogenic variant identified and known to be in trans</i>	Yes	<p>Consistent with a genetic diagnosis of disorder X</p> <p>OR</p> <p>Consistent with a genetic diagnosis of (“Gene name”)-related disorder</p>	<p>High likelihood that the variants are causative of the disorder</p> <p><i>>90% certainty that each variant is pathogenic</i></p>
<i>Recessive disorder with two likely pathogenic variants identified and known to be in trans</i>	Yes	<p>Consistent with a genetic diagnosis of disorder X</p> <p>OR</p> <p>Consistent with a genetic diagnosis of (“Gene name”)-related disorder</p>	<p>High likelihood that the variants are causative of the disorder</p> <p><i>>90% certainty that each variant is pathogenic</i></p>

<i>Recessive disorder with two pathogenic variants identified where not known if variants are in trans</i>	Yes	Consistent with a genetic diagnosis of disorder X OR Consistent with a genetic diagnosis of (“Gene name”)-related disorder	High likelihood that the variants are causative of the disorder <i>>99% certainty that each variant is pathogenic</i>
<i>Recessive disorder with one pathogenic and one likely pathogenic variant identified where not known if variants are in trans</i>	Yes	Consistent with a genetic diagnosis of disorder X – parental testing required	Likely that the variants are causative of the disorder <i>>90% certainty that each variant is pathogenic</i>
<i>Recessive disorder with two likely pathogenic variants identified where not known if variants are in trans</i>	Yes	Possible genetic diagnosis of disorder X – parental testing required	Likely that the variants are causative of the disorder <i>>90% certainty that each variant is pathogenic</i>
<i>Recessive disorder with one (likely) pathogenic variant and a reportable VUS*</i>	Yes	Possible genetic diagnosis of disorder X – additional evidence required to clarify this result	When it is not possible to obtain sufficient evidence to classify the VUS as likely pathogenic but all the available clinical, gene-level and variant-level evidence supports the likely diagnosis
<i>Recessive disorder with homozygous reportable VUS*</i>	Yes if appropriate e.g. parents are consanguineous and phenotype is consistent with gene	Variant of uncertain significance identified – consider further action <u>Clearly</u> describe in the report the action required that could change the classification to likely pathogenic	Recommend further testing or investigations that could be undertaken in order to reclassify the variant as likely pathogenic.

<i>Recessive disorder with one (likely) pathogenic variant</i>	Not usually Only appropriate in specific circumstances e.g. patient's phenotype highly consistent with the disorder and this gene	A genetic cause for the patient's clinical presentation has not been identified OR Single pathogenic variant identified – consider further action State: "...at least a carrier and this result increases the likelihood of a diagnosis of disorder X".	Either an incidental carrier finding or a second (likely) pathogenic variant has not been detected and further genetic testing is required.
<i>Recessive disorder with one VUS* identified</i>	No	A genetic cause for the patient's clinical presentation has not been identified State in the result text that the result does not exclude a genetic diagnosis	There is no clinical utility in reporting a single heterozygous VUS with potential risk of misinterpretation

*See Figure 2 for sub-classifications of variants of uncertain significance

Supplementary Table C: Additional recommendations for reporting genomic variants with reduced penetrance, hypomorphic variants and risk alleles

Classification	Variant(s) included in report?	Result summary for genomic laboratory report	Explanatory notes
<i>(Likely) Pathogenic, reduced (or low) penetrance</i>	Yes	Consistent with a genetic diagnosis of disorder X with reduced penetrance OR Associated with a genetic susceptibility to disorder X with low penetrance	Include evidence for reduced (or low) penetrance >90% certainty that the variant is pathogenic but known to be associated with reduced/low

			<i>penetrance and therefore may affect clinical management</i>
<i>Established/likely risk allele</i>	Yes (only in appropriate clinical contexts)	Consistent/associated with a genetic susceptibility to disorder X State the evidence including odds ratio and that it is common in population studies; "...it is associated with an increased risk of disorder X (OR >xxx) therefore it is likely consistent/associated with their clinical presentation"	Only for variants with sufficient evidence showing OR >2
<i>Established/likely hypomorphic variant</i>	Yes (only in appropriate clinical contexts with specific inheritance and phenotype)	Consistent with a genetic diagnosis of disorder X Clearly state that one variant is hypomorphic and is only associated with a specific phenotype and inheritance pattern	No guidelines are currently available for such variants; evidence for hypomorphic nature can include segregation analysis, phenotypic specificity, functional assays and knowledge of genetic mechanism

Supplementary Table S3: PS2/PM6 example usage

Type of test	Parental relationships confirmed by test	Gene	Phenotype	Evidence criterion
Single gene followed by parental testing of variant	No	<i>NIPBL</i>	Classical clinical presentation of Cornelia de Lange including: Facial gestalt, severe global developmental delay/intellectual disability, hirsutism, upper-limb reduction defects, growth retardation and microcephaly	PM6
Trio exome or genome with virtual panel analysis (e.g. DDG2P in DDD study or tiered variants in	Yes	<i>NIPBL</i>	Classical clinical presentation of Cornelia de Lange including: Facial gestalt, severe global developmental delay/intellectual disability, hirsutism, upper-limb	PS2

100,000 Genomes Project)			reduction defects, growth retardation and microcephaly	
Gene-agnostic trio exome or genome (variants filtered by mode of inheritance)	Yes	<i>NIPBL</i>	Classical clinical presentation of Cornelia de Lange including: Facial gestalt, severe global developmental delay/intellectual disability, hirsutism, upper-limb reduction defects, growth retardation and microcephaly	PS2
Trio exome or genome with virtual panel analysis (e.g. DDG2P in DDD study or tiered variants in 100,000 Genomes Project)	Yes	<i>NIPBL</i>	Severe developmental delay; no other features of Cornelia de Lange	NOT USED
Gene-agnostic trio exome or genome (variants filtered by mode of inheritance)	Yes	<i>NIPBL</i>	Severe developmental delay; no other features of Cornelia de Lange	NOT USED
Gene panel followed by parental testing of variant	No	Many examples	Early infantile epileptic encephalopathy	PM6
Trio exome or genome with virtual panel analysis (e.g. DDG2P in DDD study or tiered variants in 100,000 Genomes Project)	Yes	Many examples	Early infantile epileptic encephalopathy	PS2_Moderate
Gene-agnostic trio exome or genome (variants filtered by mode of inheritance)	Yes	Many examples	Early infantile epileptic encephalopathy	PS2_Moderate
Trio exome or genome with virtual panel analysis (e.g. DDG2P in DDD study or tiered variants in 100,000 Genomes Project)	Yes	Many examples	Non-syndromic Intellectual disability	PS2_Supporting
Gene-agnostic trio exome or genome (variants filtered by mode of inheritance)	Yes	Many examples	Non-syndromic Intellectual disability	PS2_Supporting

Supplementary Table S4: Examples of using phenotype specificity as evidence for PP4.

Evidence Level	Genetic aetiology	Gene(s)	Percentage of cases explained by variants in this gene or gene panel*	Phenotype	Functional evidence (e.g. biochemical, MRI, muscle biopsy)
				<i>A strong consensus supporting a clinical diagnosis of the syndrome based on the features described.</i>	
Supporting	Sotos syndrome	<i>NSD1</i>	~90%	Facial gestalt and developmental delay/ intellectual disability or childhood overgrowth (height and/or head circumference ≥ 2 SD above the mean)	N/A
Moderate	Sotos syndrome	<i>NSD1</i>	~90%	Facial gestalt and developmental delay/intellectual disability and childhood overgrowth (height and/or head circumference ≥ 2 SD above the mean)	N/A
Supporting	Kabuki syndrome	<i>KMT2D</i> and <i>KDM6A</i>	55-80%	Facial gestalt and mild-moderate developmental delay/intellectual disability	N/A
Moderate	Kabuki syndrome	<i>KMT2D</i> and <i>KDM6A</i>	55-80%	Facial gestalt, mild-moderate developmental delay/intellectual disability and one of the following ; characteristic skeletal anomalies, fetal fingertip pads, postnatal growth deficiency, hyperinsulinism	N/A
Strong	Kabuki syndrome	<i>KMT2D</i> and <i>KDM6A</i>	55-80%	Facial gestalt, mild-moderate developmental delay/intellectual disability and one of the following ; characteristic skeletal anomalies, fetal fingertip pads, postnatal growth deficiency, hyperinsulinism	Methylation signature
Supporting	Gorlin syndrome	<i>PTCH1</i> and <i>SUFU</i>	70-85%	Facial gestalt and one of the following: BCC before age 30 years or multiple BCCs >5 in a lifetime, multiple jaw keratocysts, palmar or plantar pits, non-specific radiological findings	N/A
Moderate	Gorlin syndrome	<i>PTCH1</i> and <i>SUFU</i>	70-85%	Facial gestalt and/or two of the following : BCC before age 30 years or multiple BCCs >5 in a lifetime,	N/A

				multiple jaw keratocysts, palmar or plantar pits, non-specific radiological findings	
Supporting	Cornelia de Lange syndrome	<i>RAD21</i> , <i>SMC3</i> , <i>HDAC8</i> and <i>SMC1A</i> gene panel (when no <i>NIPBL</i> variant identified)	70%	Facial gestalt and severe intellectual disability/developmental delay	N/A
Moderate	Cornelia de Lange syndrome	<i>NIPBL</i> or <i>RAD21</i> , <i>SMC3</i> , <i>HDAC8</i> and <i>SMC1A</i> gene panel (if no <i>NIPBL</i> variant identified)	70%	Facial gestalt and severe global developmental delay/intellectual disability and one of the following : upper-limb reduction defects, growth retardation and microcephaly	N/A
Strong	Hunter syndrome (MPS II)	<i>IDS</i>		Clinical and radiological features consistent with MPS II	Deficient iduronate 2-sulfatase (I2S) enzyme activity in white cells, fibroblasts, or plasma in the presence of normal activity of at least one other sulfatase.
Supporting	HNF1A/4A MODY	<i>HNF1A</i> / <i>HNF4A</i>	N/A	Diabetes	Improved glycaemic response when treated with sulphonylurea tablets
Strong	Calpainopathy	<i>CAPN3</i>	84% for cases with severe calpain-3 protein deficiency	Clinical findings consistent with calpainopathy limb girdle muscular dystrophy and raised CK	Consistent muscle biopsy findings and immunoblot analysis identifying calpain-3 protein as

					absent or severely reduced
Moderate	<i>CASK</i> – related pontocerebellar hypoplasia (PCH) in an affected female	<i>CASK</i>	N/A	PCH, moderate-severe intellectual disability, progressive microcephaly	Classical <i>CASK</i> neuroimaging findings of PCH differentiating this from other cause of PCH**
Supporting	ATRX syndrome	<i>ATRX</i>	N/A	Severe, intellectual disability in an affected male Family history compatible with X-linked recessive inheritance	HbH inclusion bodies
Moderate	ATRX syndrome	<i>ATRX</i>	N/A	Facial gestalt, severe intellectual disability in an affected male, consistent genital anomalies	HbH inclusion bodies or Methylation signature
Strong	ATRX syndrome	<i>ATRX</i>	N/A	Facial gestalt, severe intellectual disability in an affected male, consistent genital anomalies	HbH inclusion bodies and Methylation signature
Supporting	Multiple Endocrine Neoplasia type 1	<i>MEN1</i>	80-90% for familial cases	Two endocrine tumours; parathyroid, pituitary or gasto-entero-pancreatic tract	
Moderate	Multiple Endocrine Neoplasia type 1	<i>MEN1</i>	80-90% for familial cases	Two endocrine tumours; parathyroid, pituitary or gasto-entero-pancreatic tract	Somatic loss of heterozygosity at the <i>MEN1</i> locus***
Moderate	Multiple Endocrine Neoplasia type 1	<i>MEN1</i>	80-90% for familial cases	Two endocrine tumours; parathyroid, pituitary or gasto-entero-pancreatic tract and first degree relative also affected	
Moderate	Hereditary neuropathy with liability to pressure palsies	<i>PMP22</i>	100%	Recurrent focal compression neuropathies, family history consistent with autosomal dominant inheritance and absence of diabetes	Prolongation of distal nerve conduction latencies in an individual with clinical features consistent with hereditary neuropathy with liability to

					pressure palsies
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*Data from GeneReviews (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK169825/>) accessed 09/04/2026.

⁽³⁴⁾ *See CanVIG guidance for use of PP4 for cancer predisposition gene variants.

Supplementary data S5: PM2 mini-impact assessment

Introduction:

In a 2020 recommendation, ClinGen Sequence Variant Interpretation (SVI) Working Group proposed reducing the weight of PM2 to “supporting” by default (https://www.clinicalgenome.org/site/assets/files/5182/pm2_-_svi_recommendation_-_approved_sept2020.pdf). The recommendation also indicated that future adjustments to other criteria would be necessary to accommodate the change in PM2 weight. In the ACGS 2020 guidelines, there was continued support for application of PM2 at moderate level, pending a fuller revision of the ACMG guidance. A recent publication from ClinGen SVI has recommended changes to evidence weighting for missense *in silico* tools used under PP3/BP4(16).

Method:

An impact assessment was undertaken by ACGS to look at the effect of downgrading PM2, along with the proposed changes to PP3 weighting on a panel of 210 likely pathogenic variants from 85 genes, all classified using PM2_mod. Included in the assessment were 105 missense, 44 splice (mostly non-canonical or in-frame variants), 34 in-frame small indels and 27 truncating (with no NMD) variants. These variants were re-scored using PM2_sup and new PP3 weighting for missense variants based on REVEL scores from Pejaver *et al* (16) and the revised classification was recorded.

Results:

After downgrade of PM2 to supporting and application of Pejaver *et al* (16) weighting for PP3 131/210 (62.5%) variants remained likely pathogenic, 15/210 (7%) were upgraded to pathogenic and 64/210 (30.5%) were downgraded from likely pathogenic to VUS. Of the 64 that were downgraded from likely pathogenic to VUS: 19 were in-frame variants (19/64; 30%), 18 splice (18/44; 41% splice), 16 truncating (16/27; 59%) and 11 missense (11/105; 10%).

Conclusion:

The new PP3 weighting for missense variants mitigated some, but not all, of the effects of the PM2 downgrade with 10% of missense variants downgraded to VUS. However, for in-frame, truncating variants with no NMD and non-canonical/in-frame splice variants, further changes to the guidelines are required to uplift other codes, as there was a very significant impact on down classification for these variants (30-59%). Based on these results, the authors recommend that PM2 weighting is not downgraded pending implementation of ACMG v4.0 guidelines.

In addition, it is important that clear recommendations for laboratory and clinical management of variants that are downgraded due to this or other changes in guidelines are available. Loong *et al* (35) includes recommended wording for laboratory reports and guidelines for clinical genetics recontact of patients for Cancer Susceptibility Genes and may also be applicable for other rare disease cases.

Supplementary data Table S6: Table of recommendations

Number	Recommendation
1	It is essential that Clinical Scientists use their scientific and professional judgement for variant classification
2	Use of specialist VCEP guidance should be assessed for suitability by the appropriate specialist service and utilised where appropriate
3	It is essential that clinical and scientific data are both incorporated in variant classification
4	Variant classification should be undertaken independently from previously published classifications
5	Both SNV and CNV guidelines should be used for classification of CNVs
6	Use of Bayesian-derived evidence points for SNVs is recommended
7	The default recommended points for CNVs should be applied for each piece of evidence in most situations
8	Classification of mitochondrial genome variants should use ACGS Best Practice Guidelines for the Molecular Diagnosis of Mitochondrial Disease
9	Classification of non-coding variants should use recommended published guidelines
10	The approach to classifying variants in genes associated with multiple disorders or different inheritance patterns depends on disease mechanism
11	In the situation that the testing does not identify (likely) disease-causing variant(s), the report should clearly state that the result does not exclude a genetic diagnosis.
12	Variants should be reported using ISCN or HGVS nomenclature where possible
13	The variant classification should be included within the results section of the laboratory report
14	Standardised report wording should be used
15	For recurrent CNVs we recommend that those with a haploinsufficiency/triplosensitivity score of 3 (sufficient evidence) equates to a Pathogenic classification, a score of 2 (emerging evidence) equates to Likely Pathogenic, and a score of 1 (little evidence) equates to a VUS
16	VUS can be classified into three sub-groups
17	VUS should generally only be considered for reporting where there is a high level of supporting evidence and additional evidence might be obtained to allow re-classification as (likely) pathogenic
18	There may be exceptional circumstances in which an MDT discussion concludes that there is clinical utility in reporting a VUS where the potential for reclassification is unclear
19	There are specific situations where reporting a VUS would not be considered appropriate
20	Reporting of carrier status in an autosomal recessive gene as a default approach is not recommended
21	Standardised terminology for reporting of Reduced Penetrance Variants should be used e.g. "(likely) pathogenic, reduced penetrance"; "(likely) pathogenic with low penetrance and variable expressivity"
22	Risk (susceptibility) alleles may be reported in appropriate clinical contexts using standardised terminology "established" / "likely" / "uncertain" risk allele
23	Standardised terminology for reporting of Hypomorphic variants should be used
24	Reclassification of variants that affect clinical actionability should be shared and agreed with all NHS laboratories involved prior to the variant being reported
25	Variant classification data should be shared in public databases

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